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خیابان تخت جمشید شماره ۲۳۸

تلفن : ۴۲۳۱۷

تهران

29th June, 1971.

Dear Andrew,

You may not be too surprised to hear that the Museum would appreciate a visit from you. In all the circumstances this would be best undertaken before I have to leave Iran in mid-July.

I am frankly upset that you did not think to send me some sort of short note with Richard explaining what happened to you near Bushire, before I had to start coping with questions and requests for various details at this end.

If you cannot come too quickly, please send me a couple of photographs in any case. These are apparently required here.

Apart from getting all that of my chest I hope things go very well and that the survey has progressed well so far.

Yours ever,

